

OZOD SHARAFIDDINOV: A FIGURE WHERE COMPASSION AND ENLIGHTENMENT HARMONIZE

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Abstract

This article analyzes not only the scholarly legacy of the prominent literary critic Ozod Sharafiddinov but also his human qualities. In particular, it examines the memoir written by the Indian entrepreneur Govinda Ram in the 2006 issue of the journal Jahon Adabiyoti and the recollections published by Shukur Qurbon in the 10th issue of 2010. These sources highlight the scholar's mentorship, kindness, and principled strictness. Furthermore, the article provides a scholarly assessment of his religious and ethical views expressed in "G'aroyib haqiqatni kashf etdim" ("I Discovered a Strange Truth"), his aesthetic approach in "Cho'lponni anglash" ("Understanding Cho'lpon") and "G'afur G'ulomning kulgusi" ("The Laughter of G'afur G'ulom"), as well as his research work and translation mastery.

Keywords

Ozod Sharafiddinov, mentor-disciple relationship, Jahon Adabiyoti, religious thought, literary criticism, Cho'lpon, G'afur G'ulom, translation, spirituality.

Introduction

In the history of literary studies, there are scholars whose personal virtues deserve as much attention as their academic heritage. Such figures not only establish scientific schools but also leave a deep spiritual imprint on the hearts of their students. One of the brightest representatives of Uzbek literary scholarship is Ozod Sharafiddinov.

He is recognized not only as a scholar who reinterpreted the works of Cho'lpon and G'afur G'ulom from a renewed perspective, but also as a compassionate mentor, a broad-minded intellectual, and a person possessing profound religious and educational knowledge.

Research Methodology

This article employs historical-comparative, textual, and biographical analysis methods.

The texts of the scholar's works were analyzed;

Memoirs and recollections (including those by Shukur Qurbon and the Indian entrepreneur Govinda Ram) were studied;

Comparative analysis was conducted using scholarly articles and literary sources.

Through these methods, Ozod Sharafiddinov's spiritual and educational views were comprehensively examined.

Main Part

In 2006, the journal *Jahon Adabiyoti* published memoirs by the Indian entrepreneur Govinda Ram about Ozod Sharafiddinov. In them, the relationship between mentor and student is compared to paternal affection. According to Ram, Ozod Sharafiddinov treated him like his own child, frequently engaged in conversations with him, and would call with concern if he did not see him for several days.

A particularly striking event occurred when Ram's father became seriously ill. When no airline tickets were available, Ozod Sharafiddinov resolved the issue with a single phone call, enabling his student to meet his father one last time. This incident clearly demonstrates the scholar's compassion and sense of responsibility.

Similarly, the recollections of Shukur Qurbon published in the 10th issue of 2010 confirm Sharafiddinov's image as a true mentor. He supported the publication of the young writer's first book, helped him secure employment, and at crucial moments strengthened his will through strict admonition. Rather than offering mere consolation, he preferred to cultivate resilience.

In "G'aroyib haqiqatni kashf etdim," Ozod Sharafiddinov calls humanity to mutual kindness and compassion. Quoting from the Gospel, he recalls the principle: "Love your neighbors." These reflections demonstrate his religious awareness and his understanding of religion as a universal moral standard.

For Sharafiddinov, religion was not a means of division but a spiritual value guiding humanity toward moral perfection. His call to love one another and to be generous in goodness aligns harmoniously with his humanistic scholarly views.

His work "Cho'lponni anglash" is a significant study that freed Cho'lpon's творчество from ideological constraints. He interpreted Cho'lpon not through political lenses, but on the basis of aesthetic criteria.

During his research, Sharafiddinov studied early Uzbek periodicals written in the old Arabic-based script, preserved in the Turon Library in Tashkent, including *Zarafshon*, *Turkiston*, *Yosh Leninchi*, *Qizil O'zbekiston*, and *Mushtum*. This demonstrates his strong textual scholarship and mastery of the old script.

In addition, he translated numerous works. Among them were writings by Vladimir Lenin and materials related to the Kazakh statesman Dinmuhammed Qonayev. This confirms his multilingual competence and professional excellence as a translator.

In “G‘afur G‘ulomning kulgusi,” he sought to highlight the positive aspects of G‘afur G‘ulom’s творчество. This approach reflects the scholar’s intellectual integrity and objective academic stance.

Analysis And Results

In “G‘aroyib haqiqatni kashf etdim,” Ozod Sharafiddinov interprets the concept of truth from deep philosophical and religious perspectives. He calls upon individuals to pursue self-awareness, purity of heart, and spiritual maturity. His references to Biblical verses and religious concepts demonstrate his knowledge of theology and intellectual depth.

This aspect confirms that his worldview extended beyond literature alone. He regarded religion not as ignorance but as a source of enlightenment.

The memoirs of Shukur Qurbon portray Ozod Sharafiddinov as kind, generous, open-hearted, and humorous. His assistance to Ram during his father’s illness and his support in urgent travel arrangements vividly demonstrate his human virtues. This event proves that he was a moral as well as intellectual pillar for his students.

The research leads to the following conclusions:

Ozod Sharafiddinov was not only a literary critic but also a promoter of spiritual thought.

His works contain profound and well-grounded religious and educational ideas.

He played an incomparable role in continuing the mentor-disciple tradition. His legacy remains relevant in addressing contemporary spiritual challenges.

Conclusion And Recommendations

Ozod Sharafiddinov’s scholarly and spiritual heritage holds significant importance for modern society. His reflections on truth, faith, and spirituality have not lost their value in today’s era of globalization.

Recommendations:

- 1.To study his religious and educational views as a separate academic research subject;
- 2.To promote his works widely among young people;
- 3.To apply his mentorship principles in developing the mentor-disciple tradition.

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